

Assessing AI Adoption: Investigating Variances in AI Utilization across Student Year Levels in Far Eastern University-Manila, Philippines

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ABSTRACT: This study investigates the prevalent use of artificial intelligence (AI) among college students at Far Eastern University. Despite the risks, it aims to understand the primary reason behind the continuous use of AI. According to academics, the benefits of implementing AI in higher education include better inclusion, increased efficiency in administrative costs, and improvements in the learning-teaching process (Pisica et al., 2023). However, the extreme utilization of AI among students has led to cheating and plagiarism for many reasons that impact their personal lives and mental health. The researcher identified potential gaps while assessing possible solutions to lessen the student using Artificial Intelligence (AI) excessively. Moreover, the researcher used a quantitative method analysis involving 40 college students from 1st-year level to 4th-year level to explore the impacts of Artificial Intelligence on their academic tasks and learning styles. Thus, examining the utilization of AI from different year levels of Far Eastern University college students revealed that the researcher provides valuable insights into addressing the challenges posed by excessive dependency on AI while maintaining academic integrity and the need for the students to develop their critical thinking skills. After the researcher analyzed the collected data, it showed that the utilization of Artificial Intelligence (AI) for academic workloads varies among participants covering different college students, showing that first-year students rely on AI due to peer pressure. In contrast, the second-year students use it to improve their academic standing. Third-year students depend on AI because of time constraints, while fourth-year students use AI to minimize the possibility of human errors. The study conveys no significant differences in the probability of using AI for academic purposes, and it does not prevent the students from using AI regardless of their year level. Therefore, the researcher recommends proposing stricter AI checkers and educating the students on responsible Artificial Intelligence (AI) usage to mitigate academic misconduct.

KEYWORDS: potent technology, impact of AI usage, consequences of AI utilization, generating academic works, negative aspects of AI

INTRODUCTION

In today's rapidly evolving technological landscape, Artificial Intelligence (AI) has become a potent technology that can bring a fundamental transformation in the education sector, according to Seo et al. (2021). AI can analyze huge amounts of data that can provide valuable insights into the learning styles and interests of the students. As reported in an article released by Best Colleges (2023), the majority of students, 54% in particular, used artificially intelligent systems to generate their academic work, which results in cheating and plagiarizing acts. Subsequently, in 2022, Chat GPT, a chatbot with a vast language model, was launched by Open AI. It can write essays, summarize books, and solve complex arithmetic problems; it can do all these tasks almost instantly. With that, students suddenly possessed a new and useful piece of technology. However, the influence of Artificial Intelligence (AI) on the students' cultural, normative, and expectational aspects remains elusive. Furthermore, among college students, one of the most prominent problems in educational institutions is the overabundant usage of Artificial Intelligence (AI), which appears to have constituted an avenue for misconduct such as cheating Peritz (2022).

Moreover, upon reading studies about the excessive use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) among college students, the researchers identified some gaps while formulating potential solutions. Gaps include knowing how often these students use artificial intelligence in their schoolwork, and despite knowing the consequences of doing so, they continuously use AI. On the other hand,

the gaps identified aid the researcher in having new queries for the respondents of this study, allowing them to produce a potential solution to the problem. Hence, the significance of addressing these gaps is that it will lessen the number of students who use Artificial Intelligence (AI) as their tool to have their assignments or exams done through cheating and plagiarism with the help of AI.

This research will demonstrate the underlying ramifications of having artificial intelligence (AI) and how it shapes the overall study habits of college students. Subsequently, through an in-depth examination of this matter, researchers will be able to investigate both its implications for persisting utilization alongside the negative aspects of using it in modern times, as well as the plausible explanations behind the students opting to utilize Artificial Intelligence (AI) in their school assessments despite knowing the risks that come with it. In this way, the current study will benefit the researchers by providing a comprehensive investigation into the rationale behind the reasons why learners keep depending on artificial intelligence even though they are aware of its repercussions.

Research Objectives

1. To determine the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - a. Year level, and;
 - b. Program.
2. To determine the likelihood of the participants using AI in their academic assessments
3. To investigate significant differences in the likelihood of utilizing Artificial Intelligence (AI) for academic assessments across different year levels among participants.

METHODOLOGY

The researchers used both descriptive and inferential analysis to gather information from first-year to fourth-year college students of FEU. The goal was to determine if AI is excessively used and identify any significant differences between the groups being studied. Considering their limited time, the researchers decided to use the quantitative analysis method for their convenience in gathering and analyzing data. Additionally, given that they conducted the study with various kinds of students, the researchers chose a quantitative approach, as they are also looking at software applications that can process and interpret data gathered promptly regardless of the extensive number of participants.

This approach helped the authors develop evidence-based recommendations for students and educators. According to Lund et al. (2021), using an EBR approach can achieve greater reliability in their conclusions and clarify areas needing further research. Furthermore, the researcher can recognize potential areas of concern and develop targeted mediation to address them by gathering quantitative data from various sources, specifically surveys. By doing so, the researcher gained valuable insights and discovered the impact of continuously using AI in completing academic tasks despite the risk.

The study's respondents were 40 College Students in Far Eastern University during the Academic Year 2020-2024. The researchers chose a Survey Questionnaire as the instrument to gather data from College Students of Far Eastern University enrolled during the Academic Year 2023-2024. According to Marshall, G. (2005), a survey questionnaire is an instrument for consistently applying scientific protocol for collecting data from respondents. Questions in the survey will answer specific research goals. The researchers selected this as the instrument because it allows them to collect a large amount of data in a short time, there is less risk of bias, and it is the easiest instrument to use for analysis and visualization regarding mass data selection. Specifically, the type of survey questionnaire the researchers chose is the Likert Scale. In Likert Scale questions, the respondents are asked to rate a particular issue on a scale ranging from Highly Likely to Highly Unlikely. Through this, abundant information was collected and analyzed for rating scale questions, a quick and straightforward way to engage respondents with surveys. In the next step, researchers asked permission from the college students to conduct a survey. Consent forms were distributed initially for the approval of the respondents. The survey questionnaires were then duplicated and distributed to the respondents. Lastly, the interpretation of data was conducted after the data gathering, and the information obtained was collected and statistically analyzed.

After providing questions in a Likert Scale survey for the college students of Far Eastern University, the researchers analyzed the collected data quantitatively to know the exact number of students that have the same reasons for utilizing artificial intelligence in their schoolwork. The researchers categorized the data collected from the respondents according to the most selected variable in the survey. Moreover, each answer was designated from the most chosen answer of the students to the least chosen

reason for their usage of artificial intelligence (AI). The researchers utilized Google Forms to collect data from the Likert Scale Survey. A QR code or link was provided so each participant could easily access the questionnaire. All the data the researchers collected was beneficial in articulating probable solutions to the problem.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Demographic Profile

Table 1. Profile of the Respondents

	Frequencies	Percentage
Year Level		
1st year	10	25%
2nd year	10	25%
3rd year	10	25%
4th year	10	25%
Program		
BS Architecture	2	5%
BS Marketing Management	5	12.5%
BS Tourism Management	12	30%
BS Nursing	5	12.5%
BS Entrepreneurship	2	5%
BS Psychology	4	10%
BA Communication	3	7.5%
BS Accountancy	6	15%
BS Medical Technology	1	2.5%
TOTAL	40	100.00%

Table 1 shows the respondents' profiles regarding year level and program. The table includes 40 respondents, with ten individuals from each level, resulting in 25%. In terms of the Program, 30% of the respondents are from BS Tourism Management, 15% are from BS Accountancy, 12% are from BS Nursing, 10% are from BS Psychology, 7.5% are from BA Communication, 5% are from BS Entrepreneurship and BS Architecture, and the 2.5% are from BS Medical technology.

B. Likelihood of using AI in their Academic Assessments

Table 2. Likelihood of using AI in their Academic Assessments

Indicators	M	SD	Interpretations	Rank
1. I am knowledgeable enough to utilize artificial intelligence in my academic assessments.	3.075	0.829	Highly Likely	1
2. I am most likely to depend on Artificial Intelligence in completing my assessments.	2.375	0.838	Likely	7
3. Utilizing artificial intelligence (AI) has been beneficial to me intellectually.	2.375	0.893	Likely	7
4. Utilizing artificial intelligence makes me feel at risk.	2.750	0.981	Likely	2
5 One of the many reasons why I prefer to utilize Artificial Intelligence is because I have heavy workloads.	2.500	0.847	Likely	4
6. Peer Pressure is among the factors that make me favor to use artificial intelligence	2.350	0.864	Likely	8

7. My preference for using artificial intelligence stems in part from an insufficient amount of time.	2.550	0.846	Likely	3
8. Laziness is one of the reasons why I use artificial intelligence.	2.436	0.968	Likely	5
9. I chose to use artificial intelligence because I prioritize other things more.	2.175	1.130	Likely	9
10. I often use Artificial Intelligence as a tool because I lack knowledge in a certain topic.	2.475	0.933	Likely	6
11. I utilize Artificial Intelligence to enhance my Academic Performance	2.550	0.932	Likely	3
12. I used Artificial Intelligence because it helps to reduce the chances of human error.	2.550	0.914	Likely	3
OVERALL MEAN	2.511	0.914	LIKELY	

Legend: 0.00 – 1.00 (highly unlikely), 1.01 – 2.00 (unlikely), 2.01 – 3.00 (likely), 3.01 – 4.00 (highly likely)

Table 2 shows the outcomes and reasons why Far Eastern University relies on artificial intelligence (AI) and why the students experience excessive use of it.

Indicator 1 states, "I am knowledgeable enough to utilize artificial intelligence in my academic assessments." It has the highest average mean of 3.075 and a standard deviation of 0.829, interpreted as Highly Likely, ranked 1. Given the result, most participants believe they have acquired adequate knowledge about artificial intelligence (AI). As per Sibanda et al. (2023), Artificial intelligence can enhance education by improving efficiency, speed, and productivity, thereby reducing the burden on educators while benefiting students. This implies that there is a growing acceptance and trust in the potential of AI to improve educational assessment, efficiency, and speed in the assessment process among the participants.

Indicator 4, which states that "Utilizing artificial intelligence makes me feel at risk," acquired an average mean of 2.750 and a standard deviation of 0.981, interpreted as Likely, ranked 2. The result shows that students still rely on AI for their academic work despite feeling at risk. However, it is crucial to note that AI is designed to offer additional support to enhance their educational performance (Dwivedi et al., 2023).

Indicators 7, 11, and 12 have the same total mean, wherein indicator 7 has a standard deviation of 0.893, indicator 11 has a standard deviation of 0.932, and indicator 12 has a standard deviation of 0.914, which they are interpreted as Likely, ranked 3. Indicators 7, 11, and 12 have the same total mean, wherein indicator 7 has a standard deviation of 0.893, indicator 11 has a standard deviation of 0.932, and indicator 12 has a standard deviation of 0.914, which they are interpreted as Likely, ranked 3. Considering the results, most participants will likely use Artificial intelligence due to time constraints to improve their academic performance and mitigate human error. According to Pedró et al. (2019), students optimize their learning experience within a limited time frame. So, they utilize AI-powered tools that help them navigate through the course material more efficiently and effectively, especially with their busy schedules. Therefore, students can allocate more time and energy to complex assignments that require critical thinking and creativity.

In summary, the overall mean of the outcomes and reasons why the Far Eastern University relies on artificial intelligence (AI) and why the students experience excessive use of it has 2.511 interpreted as Likely. The respondents revealed that their Artificial Intelligence (AI) usage has helped them complete academic tasks and improve productivity in their personal lives regardless of the risk. However, some students indicate that excessive use of AI negatively impacts their mental and physical health.

C. Comparison

Table 3. ANOVA

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	0.691403	3	0.230	0.978	0.414	2.866
Within Groups	8.485342	36	0.236			
Total	9.176745	39				

After analyzing the collected data, we observed distinctive patterns in using artificial intelligence (AI) for academic assessments among participants at various academic levels. Moreover, we sorted out the most probable and least likely reasons for using AI after carefully analyzing the causes of action supplied by participants from each year level. As per the data collected, peer pressure is the primary reason driving first-year students' reliance on AI, whereas second-year students utilize it mostly to improve their academic standing. Furthermore, the third-year students' most likely rationale is that they did not have enough time, while the fourth-year students' top-ranked reasoning is to decrease the possibility of human error. Having stated that, we were able to ascertain that each year, the level of motivation for using artificial intelligence (AI) tools varies.

Given in the table where the P value is greater than 0.05 illustrates that there are no significant differences in the likelihood of utilizing Artificial Intelligence (AI) for academic purposes across different year levels among participants. Hence, this shows that even those who are from first-year levels and second-year levels have the same frequency of usage of Artificial Intelligence as the third-year and fourth-year levels students in completing their coursework which also implies that their differences in their year levels do not limit them from utilizing AI as they use it to expedite their coursework.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this paper aims to determine the reasons for the continuous use of artificial intelligence by students at FEU Manila despite knowing the risks that come with it. The researchers acquired information using a survey in the form of a Likert scale that was conducted through a Google Form on selected students from 1st year to 4th year, and the result was analyzed using a quantitative analysis that aided the researcher in acquiring the fundamental reason for the reliance of learners on Artificial Intelligence in their coursework. Most students choose to depend on AI to complete their assessment as their primary reason. According to an article written by Seo et al. (2021), students who rely too much on Artificial Intelligence become too dependent on using it, which could lead to excessive control on utilizing AI, which could both have a negative and positive impact on their performance in school. Moreover, the researchers were also able to find how such reasons affect how students cope with difficulties in their studies. This reveals that students opted to use AI in completing their coursework, which implies their rapid dependence on AI, possibly negatively impacting their oral performance as they depend most on AI. Lastly, the students chose the insufficient time for their usage of AI, which implies that they could experience heavy workloads that they left with insufficient time to complete their course, leading them to utilize AI more easily. Though utilizing AI has a positive impact, for it helps the students to have a better quality of work and be able to acquire new information, excessive usage of it also has a negative impact on them as it could lead them to be dependent on it and could hinder them from learning orally to finish their coursework on themselves.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Our research indicates that students primarily use artificial intelligence because they rely on it for academic purposes. Yet, some students still use artificial intelligence to check on some work on their school tasks. According to the article by Masaryk University, (n.d.), usage of AI applications that directly impact the content of assignments, such as written papers, must be disclosed. It is not required to disclose the use of an AI program if it is just employed for formal text editing. As it said, there are still AIs that can help students with their school tasks. However, direct content is a different issue when doing assignments using AI. Considering this, we recommend that school administrators reduce instances of plagiarism and cheating among students by implementing more stringent artificial intelligence (AI) checkers and other tools. Furthermore, instruct students on the responsible use of AI, highlighting the constraints of extensive language models. Foundry (2023). As stated, this has concerns and challenges for academic purposes (Estrellado, C. J., 2023). We also suggest that students learn how to manage using AI since AI tools are educated on enormous volumes of data, and it is possible that they would generate the same material repeatedly, which could result in plagiarism and cheating.

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